

Discover the Power of the OpenAIRE Graph

An Interconnected Web of Scientific Knowledge

The OpenAIRE Graph creates an interconnected web of scientific knowledge, making it one of the world's most trusted resources.

A Community-Driven Public Good

The OpenAIRE Graph is created for and by the Open Science community with its roadmap steered by OpenAIRE AMKE, a non-profit organisation, members.

Open

The OpenAIRE Graph by design follows FAIR principles and its data is open; anyone can access and take advantage of it.

Transparent

The OpenAIRE Graph's data provenance is fully tracked and documented.

Interconnected

The OpenAIRE Graph links data to organisations, funders, projects, and people, ensuring comprehensive connectivity.

Trusted

The OpenAIRE Graph has been under constant development with the support of the European Commission since 2008 and will be the authoritative source for the EOSC EU Node.

Ready to Transform Your Research?

Get Started with the
OpenAIRE Graph Today!

graph.openaire.eu

 [@OpenAIREGraph](https://twitter.com/OpenAIREGraph)

Designed for Open Science

Empowering
Open Scholarly Communication

Your partner in

- + Scientific Discovery
- + Bibliometrics
- + Open Science Monitoring

Beyond Publications

Includes data, software, patents, and other types of research products for a 360° view of research.

Provenance and Transparency

All results linked to their original sources. All inferences with a confidence score.

Comprehensive Analysis all in one place

Includes citations and advanced citation analytics from **BIP! Finder**.

Co-Authorship Networks

Relationships between authors, institutions, and countries to identify partnerships and collaborators.

Interconnected Research Networks

Research outputs linked to authors, institutions, and grants. Beyond PIDs, assisted by AI.

Interdisciplinarity, social & economic impact

Fields of Science and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) classifications.

Comprehensive OA Monitoring

Open Access routes to evaluate Transformative Agreements and assess Plan S compliance.

Regular Updates

Stay up to date with monthly releases.

Advanced Visualisation

Use OpenAIRE's interactive dashboards and customisable reports to track research metrics, identify trends, and present findings effectively.

Deduplication for Trusted Statistics

Deduplicated records from different sources for precise analysis and reporting.

View our work in

Open Science MONITOR - monitor.openaire.eu
Irish OA Monitor - oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu
EOSC Observatory - eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu

Open Science Monitoring

Bibliometrics

Scientific Discovery

